

Solutions for Digital Interaction of a Resilient Energy Community in a Service-oriented Framework

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Abstract—Energy communities are emerging entities which need their own Information and Communication System. Resilience is an important metric of such communities, and it has to be implemented for both energy supply versus public network outages and for its information system versus cyber-attacks, acting as cyber-citadels which have to resist external malicious attacks while having also digital interactions with external entities. The paper presents solutions for a resilient energy community with appropriate implementations of digital interaction for data exchange, in order to acquire external energy service for specialized companies and to deliver also information and communication-related services for external users. Principles of a Contractual Data Protection Regulation are presented, as an adaptation of data protection tailored for automated energy services and based on secure data exchange. The principles are verified in an H2020 demonstration project which has also two external entities with digital interaction.

Keywords—energy communities, resilience, ICT, energy services, cyber-security, Contractual Data Protection Regulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Energy communities are emerging entities everywhere in the world. They have as primary purpose to serve a community of people with necessary energy for their daily life and activity, thus enabling also resiliency and a sustainable local development.

A review of community based microgrids (CBMG) deployments is presented in [1]. The work shows the importance of agent-based model (ABM) systems in microgrids, energy security, local energy markets and peer-to-peer (P2P) interactions, thus raising the importance of the Information and Telecommunication Technology (ICT) aspects related to CBMG activities. In [2] is analysed a transactive energy model helped by blockchain technology, considering that this supports a fundamental mechanism to any economic transaction which is trust between the parties.

The study presented in [3] is linking peer-to-peer energy trading to the essential activity of local energy communities, also describing a specific case study which compares local, centralized, distributed, hierarchical and P2P control architectures. The data flow is analysed in terms of impact on

microgrid control in the case of communication failure, keeping the study mainly in a technical area.

A trading framework for smart grids in neighbourhood area networks is analysed in terms of data security in [4]. The paper raises the issue of preserving privacy beyond providing ways of hiding user's electricity consumption. The presented framework outperforms the state-of-the-art solutions in terms of privacy protection and trading flexibility in a prosumer-to-prosumer (point to point-based architecture) design.

Data Protection and Cybersecurity Certification Activities and Schemes in the Energy Sector are considered in [5], where it is discussed the privacy and security of ICT products, services, and processes versus certification schemes for the needed ICT activity, while considering General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) aspects as well. In the study view, a complex constellation of implementation models would require careful design to avoid proliferation and disincentivising of stakeholders. The paper shows the complexity of the subject "processing operations" of data and its certification, especially when it is about involving personal data, failing in the full area of GDPR [6]. Resilience is an important asset which is seen in energy communities at least in two different ways: as energy resilience and as being a cybersecurity aspect. In [7] it is discussed the European Cybersecurity Strategy in terms of cyber resilience, which is rather new subject pointing on the „ability of the system to prepare, absorb, recover, and adapt to adverse effects, especially those associated with cyberattacks”, as defined by Alexander Kott and Igor Linkov. While cyber resilience is an increasingly complex subject, the energy resilience is of equal importance, as energy is an essential prerequisite for any activity. Study [8] proposes a metrics for the energy resilience, having four main aspects - physical, information, cognitive and social, organized in a complex resilience matrix, with the conclusion that it is a need for integrating all these aspects.

The cyber-physical security at protocol level is discussed in [9], with reference to SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition), DERs (Distributed Energy Resources) and advanced metering infrastructures. It identifies gaps for a defence model in a system with multiple distribute energy resources and with substantial use of small type equipment

such as Raspberry Pi or similar, showing that there are multiple vulnerabilities for the communication with DERs. This may suggest that DER can be better protected if the access to their data is not directly externally available, which can be considered also as an input for the system concepts presented in the next section.

In [10] are analysed which are state of the art authentication, access control, and secure Integration in Smart Grid, which has a similar target as an energy community need in order to interact in a digital manner with various external entities. Network gateways are seen as essential pieces of the needed architecture for a comprehensive implementation.

An ICT system of an energy community may manipulate both community and personal data, the latest being subject of GDPR consent and rules. It is normal therefore that a data exchange of a community with external entities need mirroring of data processing already established inside the community, thus it is relevant for community data exchange the Protection of personal data, as described in [11] and as analysed in different works.

Each of these studies is covering a part of the whole problem. It gives a strong signal that microgrids activities need extensive use of transactions. However, rules related to such transactions, especially in terms of legal engagement and on the use of the involved data, which may be described by mutual decisions inside a contract, is not fully developed in further works and does not have a holistic approach. Moreover, most of the cited studies see energy communities as different entities inside the community which need to interact between each other rather than an aggregation needing consolidated interactions with external entities. These external actors are not by default trustable, as they are not part of the community. Such entities can enforce however their trustfulness through contracts and data management rules before stating P2P or other ICT related interactions.

With such complexity it is a need to choose in practice valid subsets of principles to be able to cover as much as possible principles which work for an energy community.

II. DIGITAL INTERACTIONS FOR AN ENERGY COMMUNITY

Energy communities need at least two types of interactions with external world, as per Fig. 1: a) a physical interaction with various distant generation units through an electrical grid – which is usually the public network, and b) a cyber-secure ICT interaction with various actors – Energy service companies (ESCOs), suppliers, energy markets and so on, which is usually supported by communication through internet.

Fig. 1. Physical and digital (cyber) interaction of an energy community

Usually, the existence of two levels of interaction (grid and ICT) is also associated with the term of “Smart Grid”. However, in the case of an energy community it is not a focus on the smartness of the grid, but rather of the smartness of the energy community, to act as an independent and resilient entity which need to interact with public grid and with actors as per Fig. 1. This is an essential change of focus, as the community can be smart or very smart even if the public network is not keeping the same rhythm in terms of innovation. In this respect, the energy community acts nearer to the concept of using a “microgrid” [12], which has both a local electrical network as well as the property of being operated in a controlled, coordinated way.

III. ICT SOLUTIONS AND SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE FOR AN ENERGY COMMUNITY

The concepts proposed in this paper, in order to serve a resilient energy community which, need digital interactions with external actors are the following:

- The energy community is seen a “citadel” which needs to maintain virtual “walls” against any external aggression, which includes cyber-attacks. Power outages or blackouts are seen as well as aggression from the citadel point of view, considered as a supply cut-off threat.
- The reason of being protected with “walls” is that the energy community need to live in a resilient way and need to become sustainable on medium- and long-term periods. The internal activity of the community asks therefore to survive even in harsh external situations.
- From ICT perspective, it means that basic ICT functionality need to be always operational for (and inside) the community even if communication with outside environment is down (e.g., due to internet blackout) and if there are malicious cyber-attacks.
- The energy community need at the same time to be able to acquire in a digital and automatic way specific services from external entities, e.g., optimization services from ESCOs, and to provide services to other entities, e.g. VPP (Virtual Power Plant) and DR (Demand Response) aggregation with outside energy entities needing eventually as well SCADA for monitoring and dispatch, by using its internal electronic platforms. This means that it is needed a secure platform concept which allows both types of services using a cyber-secure solution.
- Moreover, data need to be considered as being potentially sensitive, so any electronic data exchange need to have specific rules for each information. In this respect, the GDPR which is applicable to individuals, need an adaptation to protect as well valuable information for the community which has to be kept secret against external actors, unless it is needed for an objective reason accepted by the community. An equivalent of GDPR, to be applied to the community’s data, is therefore needed to be designed and adopted.

Different ICT solutions exist for implementing those services, analysed on section one. The SCADA related processes – seen as hardcore critical services, ask for solutions specific to so called “critical infrastructures”. However,

services which imply data exchange and processing with external actors can be better related to MIS (Management Information System) solutions, which need cautious interaction with SCADA through well-defined data exchange rules, but also flexible and secure interaction with the external actors which provide or receive digital services.

In any such situation, the digital interaction with such actors needs therefore to have clear rules and description which is beyond ICT itself. To become compulsory obligations, these rules need to be linked eventually to legal frameworks such as contracts.

The notion of contract needs therefore to apply for any ICT interaction through automatic data exchange between parts. The following information should be part of the contract content description:

- Period of validity (from Date-Time 1 to Date-Time 2) during which a specified set of data will be exchanged with the external actor.
- Type of information which has been decided to be exchanged: clear list of measurements and parameters to be sent to the external actor (e.g., ESCO), considered to be necessary for performing the service. In this respect, a good practice should be that there is no “give me all data and I sort what I need”, but rather strictly necessary data, based on the need.
- Anonymization, where is needed and where this is possible for the scope of the contract; usually this can be obtained either by using depersonalized names for the data source and/or by providing statistical data rather than raw data which can be later processed for obtaining statistical data.
- Time granularity for each data to be exchanged: there is an important difference of content between rich information given e.g., each 1 second and information which is sent every hour or even once per day.

In this concept, the data policy profile of a certain contract with an ESCO as for a *Contractual Data Protection Regulation* (C-DPR or Contractual DPR), to emphasize the scope related to a “contract”, as an adapted approach of GDPR in the case of digital interaction between two entities which need data exchange.

Fig. 2 shows the place of a C-DPR in a contractual relation which implies data flow between parts, seen as an electronic Annex to be distributed to both parts.

Fig. 2. Data flow concept based on Contractual DPR (C-DPR)

To be noted that the knowledge owner (e.g., the ESCO) must implement a similar C-DPR policy, and this policy has to contain an additional aspect namely *Data Retention Regulation (DRR)*, which should implement deletion of used data for the service after a certain time period after contract is finished (also shown in Fig. 2). This allows eventually automatic deletion with log of the operation which should be digitally signed and handled as a proof to the data owner.

Time granularity control within the C-DPR is an important aspect of the C-DPR. A simple analysis on the Fig. 3 and 4 show the difference between various time granularities:

- Fig. 3 shows a graph based on data which is available each 1 or 2 seconds – which can be easily obtained with new smart meters by using its SCADA-like features offered by internal measurements, obtainable through a digital interface, e.g., RS4985/Modbus.

- Fig. 4 shows a graph with a rougher granularity, for instance average data each 1 hour, which is more usual in digital meters used by distribution system operators (DSOs) for invoicing or by transmission system operators (TSOs) for some operational purposes.

Fig. 3. Rich data based on small time interval (1 second) based on real-time data obtained from a smart meter.

Fig. 4. Averaged data obtained from a smart meter, based on one-hour intervals.

To be observed that while the rich data with 1-second resolution (Fig. 3) shows eventually intimate information such as e.g., short-time light in the bathroom during the night or, in this case, start-up of refrigerator’s compressors in a user’s house, the less dense information (case with 1-hour time resolution, Fig. 4) is hiding most of the internal and confidential information, while still having the potential to give the necessary information needed for an ESCO to perform a specific service. This aspect can be essential for a good practice regarding the agreed time granularity inside C-DPR based contracts.

IV. DEMONSTRATORS

At University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (UPB) have been implemented a part of the above concepts in a community-like demonstrator which is simulating a district energy system in the framework of European project WEDISTRICK [13].

Fig. 5 shows the type of interactions with external actors which are considered in the demonstrator. As UPB is the main energy community (EnCom1) in the lower part of the Fig. 5, there are two types of considered services:

- received services for EnCom1 from different ESCOs, which are represented at the left upper side of the picture considering a generic ESCO providing “ESCO services” and
- delivered services provided by EnCom1 (“EnCom services”) to an external energy community 2 - EnCom2, which can be seen as a project follower).

The role of ESCO is taken by one of the project partners [14] and the automatic data exchange is supported in a secure way through an API key which is generated automatically after contract signature.

A follower aiming for future replication of a part of the developed technologies is the Technical University of Moldova (TUM) [15]. TUM takes the role of an external community which is not big enough to operate at this stage its own ICT system, thus looking for SCADA acquisition and dispatch services from the main energy community, while additional services can be also provided, such as its aggregation in the main EnCom Virtual Power Plant or in a Demand Response program. The secure data exchange is supported by https secure connection by using also username and password as credentials – to support dispatch and VPP/DR monitoring services, while SCADA acquisition services are provided through secure VPN communication, as part of the “critical infrastructure” approach specific to utility / energy related SCADA applications.

Fig. 5. Main energy community (UPB) in interaction with external actors

To be observed that real-time services, either delivered or provided, as well as electronic contracts exchange, are using exclusively the internet as communication pathway, while data exchange is secured through a set of proven ICT solutions, meaning API keys for electronic services provided by external entities, https for dispatch services, VPN for

secure SCADA acquisition – RTUs and Smart Meters (SM) and digital signature for electronic contracts.

A view of the local dispatch of the energy community, envisioned as a “district” community, is presented in Fig. 6. The Figure shows in real-time the renewable energy production of a section of the district energy community, in terms of active and reactive power as well as of index of produced energy (kWh). The measurements have been obtained from meters which can have metrology features, to provide enforced metrological data to be used eventually in contracts between parts. The smart meters are used for both energy measurement (active and reactive energy in both directions) as well for acting as Remote Terminal Units which are integrated in a SCADA system. For the SCADA support, active and reactive power, currents and voltages are provided in real-time for each phase, while other information is also available, such as grid frequency, power factor, phase-to-phase (line) voltages, thus bringing also some data acquisition redundancy.

Fig. 6. Real time PV production evolution in UPB

To be noted that the demonstrator has a heterogeneous portfolio of PV inverters, which might bring as well, in case of using for data acquisition the specific software of each vendor, a heterogeneous data information in terms of sampling periods. The implemented solution of the demonstrator uses however a unique source of acquisition through the smart meters mounted for each PV inverter at its point of common coupling (PCC), thus obtaining coherence for all PCCs, while also simulating the real-life implementation of PV connection at the PCC with the DSO, which is also always based on a meter.

An example of monitoring historical data from PV production inside the district is shown in Fig. 7, with a time resolution of one record / minute, while detailed evolution is also available at higher time resolution (upper left graph of the same Figure).

Fig. 7. Example of process monitoring in UPB demonstrator: PV inverter power evolution in two different days

As depicted in Fig. 5, several external entities can interact based on contracts with C-DPR profiles, while the demonstrator considered representative cases which cover the main parts of the concept. Fig. 8 shows an example of implementing the C-DPR profiling, to be parameterized by the admin belonging to the community, which acts as a trustful part which defines “the rules of the game”.

For instance, if a certain variable is a data which has been agreed by the contractual parts to be available only once per hour, the time granularity for that specific data is set accordingly, while other data may have a different profile (e.g., they can be obtained each 1 minute). The Figure shows also that the contract needs to be activated after variables specific rights are fully described, and then an API key becomes available for the ESCO to perform automatic digital requests based on secure data exchange.

Fig. 8. Example of contract based C-DPR parameterisation

The admin role is intended not to have access to the data itself, but only to define its rules of usage, thus it has the function of a Data Access Point Manager (DAM), which is also one of the methods for data manipulation envisioned in Smart Metering [16] and which is pursued also in the concept of Smart Metering Gateway, as part of Germany’s DENA approach [17], having basic concepts presented in [18].

For implementing the contractual agreements associated to the energy services, the following two external users are considered to be parameterized by DAM for the demonstrator:

- An external ICT partner – as being the user ExPart_1, which needs data from EnCom1 in order to provide services. In the project setup, the energy community (which is a green energy district) acts therefore as a consumer of various services by receiving them from the ESCO. Several types of energy services can be considered, e.g. production and load prediction by using e.g. artificial intelligence technologies, optimization of energy community operation, backup storage for vital information, all being ruled by specific C-DPR’s for each different service.
- The second external partner – as user ExPart_2 (EnCom2 having as physical partner TUM), has the role to receive services from EnCom1. Here it is implemented a reversed role for the main community, compared with the previous case. Between the offered services, the following ones are considered: dispatch services with SCADA support in electrical grid of ExPart_2 and possible integration in the community in a VPP or in a load shedding cluster (thus

performing in each case different types of aggregations).

In terms of ICT measures, the ExPart_1 entity has mainly a secure data exchange based on API keys, which are available after finalizing the digital contract procedure.

The second entity ExPart_2 has mainly secure data exchange based on user credentials - username and password for login and VPN-based acquisition, obtained also within the digital contract C-DPR rights.

Fig. 9, 10 and 11 show SCADA support services provided by EnCom1 to ExPart_2, which in this case are real-time dispatch services with one view shown in Fig. 9 and historical data analysis for powers and for voltage level in Fig. 10 and 11. To be noted that ExPart_2 does not need any dispatch infrastructure, as its dispatch services is provided remotely by EnCom1 through a secure https session with specific credentials. In the specific implemented case, the SCADA service deals with a measurement point in the TUM premises, in this case the consumption of an external area belonging to the university, which contains also an astronomic observatory (as is shown in Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Dispatch services provided to TUM external energy community

Fig. 10. Example of process monitorisation in TUM follow-up demo case: power evolution on each phase, in a 24 hours interval

Fig. 11. Example of process monitorisation in TUM follow-up demo case: Voltage evolution on each phase, in a 24 hours interval

The SCADA services are enabled by smart meter data acquisition provided through a VPN, corresponding to Fig. 5 architecture. The external entity role allows its aggregation in EnCom1 structures (in a VPP or DR aggregation belonging to EnCom1), thus willing to offer the pool of resources assets such as a consumption portfolio to be coupled with the RES of the main entity.

The demonstrator's setup is organized such that a myriad of combinations becomes possible with the flexible ICT-based contractual C-DPR framework, thus allowing various types of services locally as well as remote.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents a solution of service-oriented ICT platforms to serve digital interactions of a resilient energy community, such as a "green energy" district from a smart city. Essential aspects of the concept are implemented in a pilot project in University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest / Romania and has contract-based alike services with two external entities, a partner of the project acting as an ESCO, and a second energy community entity which obtains services from the main energy community, such as data acquisition, dispatch and aggregation services in a simplified demo case.

The approach combines several concepts which can bring viable solutions for such resilient energy communities, to acquire or provide automated digital services based on ICT, with contractual models to ensure Contractual-DPR's (C-DPR), with included details such as Data Retention Regulation (DRR).

Following work will be focused on more complex and detailed implementations and on refinements of the concepts and of the automation progress towards a full chain digitalization of such bidirectionally provided services, which will include blockchain and other necessary technologies.

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